

FACTORS OF ELIMINATING IDEOLOGICAL THREATS IN THE PROCESS OF GLOBALIZATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12152621>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 6-iyun 2024 yil
Ma'qullandi: 9-iyun 2024 yil
Nashr qilindi: 19-iyun 2024 yil

KEY WORDS

*globalization, ideology, thought,
ideological weapon, moral immunity.*

ABSTRACT

In today's process of globalization, the socio-economic development of mankind has changed radically. As a result of these changes, a number of urgent and significant problems have arisen, the sphere of influence of which covers the world community, and which determine the future social development of mankind. These problems are called global problems of humanity, and it is desirable to concentrate the efforts of all countries in order to find their solution.

Introduction:

Of the global problems, the problem of maintaining peace and disarmament is the most universally important, because if this problem is not solved, the future of life and civilization on Earth will inevitably be in a very sad state. In the history of mankind, according to some data, there have been more than 14,000 wars, and unfortunately, military conflicts and conflicts are still taking place in different regions of our planet. However, at the global level, this problem intensified in the 20th century, when two world wars took place, in which more than 70 million people died. Currently, the United States, the Russian Federation, the United Kingdom, France, China, India and Pakistan are officially recognized nuclear weapons states of the world community.

Mirziyoev.Sh.M. We will resolutely continue our path of national development and raise it to a new level.

War and military conflicts are taking place in different regions of the world. Due to military operations and civil wars, some countries have reached a situation of humanitarian disaster. Examples of this include Syria, Iraq, Libya, Somalia, Afghanistan, South Sudan and other countries.

As a result of rapid changes in the information society, the acceleration of the process of globalization in the 20th century and the beginning of the formation of a global civilization changed the character of world ideologies. The lack of a powerful ideology to replace them, and the change in geopolitical goals, have strengthened the negative impact of these ideas. In such conditions, only a nation that has clearly defined its goal, has a good understanding of its needs and interests, has its own beliefs, and in a word, has formed its own national idea, will

preserve its future and determine its prospects. The Uzbek people, formed as such a nation, on the basis of their centuries-old national idea, enrich the worldview of young people with advanced technologies, realize their identity based on various influences, respect national values and carry aesthetic culture into the future. z is always ready to deliver.

In the process of analyzing this article, the methods of logicity, historicity, consistency and objectivity of scientific knowledge were widely used. Factors to eliminate moral threats in the process of globalization were widely covered. Sh.M. Mirziyoyev's works were identified as a methodological source.

Today, in the process of globalization, the ideological and ideological struggle, that is, the attempt to ideologically divide the world, is intensifying. Of course, in such a situation, strengthening our independence, ensuring its stability, prosperity, peace and future is the highest duty of each of us.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoev, speaking about various attacks against spirituality in the context of globalization: "Today, the danger of various disasters such as religious extremism, terrorism, drug addiction, human trafficking, illegal migration, and" mass culture is increasing around us if we take into account that it is growing stronger, the deep meaning and importance of these words will be more clearly evident.

The national spiritual and moral principles embedded in the heart and mind of a person make him to be honest, pure, educated, in the service of the people throughout his life, to contribute to the prosperity and development of the Motherland, as a conscious and free observer continuously encourages him to mature.

For this reason, it is important for the members of our society to comprehensively explain to the general public the strategy of actions for independent development of Uzbekistan, the goals and objectives of the Uzbek people to build a great state, and to make clear the real essence of the globalization process and its role in the aesthetic culture of the society. delivery has become one of the urgent tasks.

In the conditions of globalization, protecting the people, especially the growing youth, from spiritual threats, instilling the ideas of goodness into their hearts is being consistently implemented in all spheres of society's life. It is required to use effective methods and tools of education, promotion and propaganda at all stages of the educational system. Today, President Sh.M. Mirziyoev expressed his opinion about the connection of globalization with our social life, *"New threats, including the danger of" mass culture "and the mood of gentrification, the loss of morals and values. This is of great importance in the current globalization situation, where the danger is emerging. Therefore, in my opinion, today it is more important than ever to preserve and enrich the sources that define the human spiritual world, the culture of peoples"*.

We are witnessing that Uzbekistan is experiencing a period of national renaissance in the process of independent development, while restoring our cultural heritage, national traditions and values, the conflict between good and evil in the world is increasing. Any ideology will be viable and effective only if it takes into account the spiritual and spiritual needs of the people, national traditions and lifestyle. Here, in the process of globalization, the task of implementing reforms on the formation of a new aesthetic culture of young people is in the center of our attention based on the national ideology.

Today, the development of the world has reached such a level that ideological struggle and spiritual potential have taken the leading place. The development of humanity is under the influence of various threats, the threats aimed at jeopardizing its security and stability, even derailing its life are increasing day by day, and now there are no weapons, but only *"thought against thought, only idea against idea"* can be fought with. Ideological struggle continues both within a society, a country, and at the international and interstate level. Currently, political forces and movements that seek to expand their sphere of influence through ideological means are becoming more and more intense. threatening ideological aggression is

intensifying. Those who resort to such aggression skillfully try to use any methods, religious and national sentiments of people, socio-economic difficulties in life to achieve their evil goals. Today, they occupy the hearts and minds of certain sections of the population, especially the youth, with their own ideas, such as subversive ideas, religious extremism, indoctrination of their ideas. Its malicious goals are becoming clear to the people. These threats are spread by various destructive forces of the world so skillfully that it is attracting many people day by day through its attractive influence. "Threat" can be understood as a local, regional, regional social and historical situation that complicates the life of a person in general and weakens the social structure directed for a specific purpose during the historical period, the political basis of the state, and moreover, it is aimed at decay. 6. Third ideas do not fail to have their effect everywhere, only if we stand together with self-confidence and fight against this destructive idea, we will contribute to the further development of our country.

Today, in the ideological landscape of the world, the activity of ideological polygons, which influence the human heart and mind and fight with various means, is becoming more and more visible. At the current stage of development, a very complex and dangerous process is taking place in the world. These are explained by the changes in the political and ideological landscape of the world, the rise to a new stage of development, and the emergence of ideological and ideological obstacles that derail the democratic development that is the basis for this development and lead to the stability of society.

In preventing ideological threats, the great thinker Abu Nasr Farabi (873-950) said that man cannot achieve perfection alone. He says that he needs to be in contact with others, their help or relationships. In this process, emphasizing the perfection of qualities in a person, he puts forward the following thoughts, "A person becomes perfect with virtues, and a person who is perfect is considered happy."

As our main goal in the fight against ideological threats is to raise the morale of the society, first of all, we must achieve a deep penetration of the national idea into the minds and hearts of citizens. It is also important to form a healthy belief among the population, especially the young generation, and harmoniously promote national and universal values among them we cannot be threatened by any threats.

Therefore, in the process of studying the scientific and spiritual heritage of our ancestors, it is necessary to consider not only scientific goals, but also the priority of spiritual education interests. It is necessary to reach such a level that our young people, in addition to studying the rich heritage left by our ancestors, also take an active part in promoting it on a global scale. As a result of this, the sense of infinite pride in the hearts of our youth will be strengthened. It is known that the feeling of pride in one's country opens a wide path in the formation of high spirituality in the human heart.

REFERENCES:

1. Abdullaeva, M., Ruzmetova, F., Madrakhimova, A., &Kazokova, M. (2022). The importance of the oral method in forming imaginations about nature in children. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 2(12), 310-312.
2. Abdullayeva, M., qiziYangibayeva, N. S., &Muxtarova, I. R. (2023). Memoryanditslaws. *ScienceandEducation*, 4(2), 93-95.
3. Yangibayeva, N., & Yusupova, M. (2022). THE CONCEPT OF PERCEPTION AND THINKING IN PSYCHOLOGY. ITS PRINCIPLES. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 2(11), 50-53.
4. Qizi, Y. N. S., Saboxon, O., Risolat, A., & Salomat, S. (2022). ORAL TEACHING METHODS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL NATURE CLASSES. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 2(11), 88-90.
5. Shernafasova, H., & Yangibayeva, N. (2022). PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEMS OF IMPROVING THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL

ORGANIZATIONS. *Инновационные исследования в современном мире: теория и практика*, 1(19), 31-34.

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